

UNIVERSAL AND LANGUAGE-SPECIFIC STRATEGIES FOR ADVERTISEMENT TRANSLATION

Khudoynazarova Dilshoda Shuxratovna

O‘zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti magistranti

dilshodaxudoynazarova@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the features of advertising language in terms of the English language advertising slogans translation. The subject of research is the analysis of adequate information transmission mechanisms and methods in the translation of advertising slogans. The object of the study is English-language advertising slogans and their translation. The purpose of the study is to identify the specific characteristics of advertising slogans, features and problems that arise in the process of their translation. The material for the study was the texts of scientific, educational and methodological literature, manuals on the theory and practice of translation, articles in periodicals, dictionaries. The following research methods were used in the work: analytical, descriptive, continuous sampling method and comparative analysis of English-language slogans and their equivalents, statistical analysis. In this work, the specific characteristics of advertising slogans, features and problems arising in the process of their translation were identified. The practical value of this work lies in the fact that the results obtained during the research can be used as demonstration and illustrative material in courses on stylistics, theory and practice of translation.

Keywords: translation, communicative task, translation transformations, advertising, advertising slogan, target audience.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, trade is the key to the comfortable existence of mankind, and its promotion depends largely on advertising. An advertising slogan is a means of attracting the recipient's attention to a certain product or brand. Adequate translation of a slogan is a guarantee of successful adaptation of a company or a product in any country with another official language. This is what causes the problem of translation of such an important aspect of advertising as a promotional slogan.

English-language slogans were chosen as the material, which is due to the prevalence and the role of English language in the world information space. Most international companies aim not to create new advertising images and subjects, but to

translate and adapt texts and commercials that have already proven effective in the markets of other countries.

The main function of advertising can be deduced from its very definition: to interact with the consumer of goods/services, to influence demand formation and sales promotion of goods using a large number of different methods and schemes [8, p. 35-36].

Such a concept as "advertising text" consists of a verbal component and a set of all extra-linguistically significant components (graphics, sounds, images, etc.). The correct combination of all these components leads to the creation of an effective advertising text.

The construction of any advertising text occurs according to certain rules with a generally accepted structure that includes four main parts: a slogan, a headline, the main advertising text, an echo-phrase [7, p. 43].

It is not always appropriate to use all four components simultaneously. Their use depends on the nature of the advertised product or service and is individual for each advertising message.

The most interesting element from the point of view of our study is precisely the advertising slogan, which carries the basic information about the advertised object and has the greatest emotional and communicative orientation.

To date, almost advertising text contains a slogan. The process of its creation is considered an independent type of advertising art, which is based on knowledge of psychology, linguistics, sociology and marketing.

METHODS

The purpose of the study is to identify the specific characteristics of advertising slogans, features and problems that arise in the process of their translation. The paper brings into light the problems of translation and localization of short advertisement texts and slogans. The study of peculiarities of translation of advertising slogans into other languages is relevant due to the development of international relations in the sphere of trade and tourism.

DISCUSSION

The language of advertising slogans has a number of specific features, the main ones being:

- brevity. In Russian and Uzbek a slogan usually consists of 3-14 words, in English - of 5-7 words. From this we can conclude that its length should correspond to the volume of human working memory;
- high readability and memorability. Achieved through the use of short words, certain vocabulary specific to the language;

- inclusion of a brand name (typical for foreign brands or for new goods and services).
- possibility of full-fledged translation into other languages;
- originality and expressiveness. The structure of slogans is characterized by the use of synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, and paronyms. Also widely used are "play" on the roots of words and such stylistic figures as antithesis, anaphora, rhetorical question, ellipsis, parallelism, etc., rhyme is used.
- full compliance with the general advertising theme;
- appropriate to the target audience;
- appealing but not aggressive nature [3, p. 7], [1, p. 80-81].
- As an element of the advertising text, the slogan performs the following basic functions:
 - influencing function (combination of emotive, aesthetic and persuasive function);
 - informative function (informing potential buyers about the benefits of of the advertised product or service);
 - attracting function (attracting attention of the target audience to the advertised product, company and its activities) [6, p. 273].

Currently, there are a large number of different approaches to the classification of slogans. According to the type of advertising object advertising slogans are divided into product, corporate and advertising campaign slogans. According to the way the information is presented, slogans are divided into two types: abstract and concrete. According to the type of information conveyed, slogans are subdivided into statement, presenting and game ones. According to the way in which the brand name is included, slogans are classified into strong and weak or linked, tied, free slogans. According to the range of use slogans are divided into slogans of wide or narrow application. According to the duration of use, slogans can be strategic or tactical. There is also a classification of slogans according to the size and number of words used: short (2-4 words), Medium (5-7 words), long (8-12 words).

Translation of advertising slogans can be one of the most difficult types of translation because it requires not only transfer of meaning, but also a creative approach. Equally important is the ability to of adapting the text of an advertising slogan to social and cultural peculiarities of the target audience. In the process of translation translators often have to resort to various rearrangements, and this is what is called translation transformations.

Among the peculiarities of slogan translation are the following contradictory aspects:

- on the one hand, its translation is not an "original creative work" [2]. The translator must not go beyond the limits set by the advertising agency when creating the original slogan;
- on the other hand, the term "transcreation" is often used in relation to the translation of advertising slogans, which refers to the process of translation in which the content is completely rewritten in the target language in order to convey the overall meaning of the original message [2].

A high-quality translation of an advertising slogan plays a key role in attracting potential customers. Therefore, the methods of translation the translator resorts to play an important role.

RESULTS

A universal strategy for the translation of advertising slogans has not yet been developed. But it should be noted that in advertising, it is important not the form of the text, but its imagery, Therefore, the translator rarely resorts to literal or literal translation. More often free translation or adaptation. This is due to the national and cultural characteristics of the audience [5, p. 73].

Knowledge of some pronounced features of English-language advertising slogans can help in developing translation strategies:

- The use of verbs in the imperative mood. The most common verbs are: buy, try, ask, get, see, feel, taste, watch, find, listen, drive, let, look, drink, do, enjoy [9, p. 27].
- The use of emotionally colored adjectives and adverbs. The most frequently used adjective is the adjective "new", which is not always conveyed by the main meaning.
- The use of personal and possessive pronouns. Both Russian- and English-language slogans are characterized by the use of the following communicative model: "we, our" - to denote the advertiser, "you, your" - to address the target audience and "they, their" - to mention possible competitors [9, p. 24]. Also to strengthen the advertising appeal is characterized by the use of personal and possessive second person pronouns.
- The use of various stylistic devices. Stylistic means of expression are responsible for figurative charge of an advertising slogan and often lead to difficulties in their translation. In translation, it is important to preserve the image of the original, above all, it is necessary to reproduce the function of the reception, and not the reception itself [4, p. 57].

The alliteration that is characteristic of the English language is very difficult to retain in translation. But if this technique carries a certain stylistic load, it should be

transferred. If the alliteration technique cannot be conveyed in Russian, rhythm, word order, rhyme and repetition can be used in various combinations instead.

The associative properties of words link the features or name of a product with what it is or with the process of its consumption. Sound imitation and onomatopoeia are used to achieve this effect. The main purpose of translating anaphora, epiphora or phonetic repetition is to preserve the positional relationship of the units. Therefore, usually when translating these stylistic means, equivalent or variant correspondences are used.

Translating rhymed slogans is especially challenging, because conveying all the lexical and semantic nuances of the source language leads to a distortion of meaning. The ideal way to translate a slogan is to create a new rhyming text with the same meaning and style.

Often an equivalent or variant correspondence is used to convey the linguistic basis and function of the expressive means. But sometimes there is no similar equivalent in the system of another language, so the translator has to resort to various kinds of transformations, such as concretization, generalization, semantic development, holistic transformation, compensation.

Wordplay and puns are rightly considered to be among the most difficult cases of stylistic translation, which cannot be conveyed without losses. The translator has to decide whether to convey content by abandoning wordplay, or keep the pun by replacing the image. It is still possible to retain wordplay in translation, but one must be careful not to get ambiguity.

Consequently, the strategy for conveying advertising slogans consists of the following steps: identifying the characteristics of the language of the advertising slogan, understanding their impact on the rational and emotional spheres of consciousness of the potential buyer and then eliminating the linguistic and cultural-ethnic barrier between the communicators. The translator must predict the reaction of the target audience to the text message in the target language. To do this, it is necessary to know not only the source and target languages, but also the specifics of national psychology, differences in cultural and historical traditions, realities [10, p. 272].

CONCLUSION

We can conclude that an advertising slogan is a special kind of advertising text, which requires certain efforts for its translation and adaptation. The translation of the metaphoric and multidimensional advertising slogan requires a deep analysis of the linguistic means of the original, the choice of suitable adaptation techniques to convey not only the meaning of the source text, but also the originality of the stylistic features of the original.

REFERENCES

1. Anis'kina N.V, Modeli analiza reklamnogo teksta: Uchebnoe posobie / N.V. Anis'kina, T.B. Kolishkina. M. : Forum, NIS INFRA-M, 2013. – 304 p.
2. Bell T. Perevodim slogani [Electronic resource] // Professional'niy perevod i upravlenie informasiey.
[URL:http://www.logrus.ru/UserFiles/Image/Knowledges/articles/Slogan_translation.pdf](http://www.logrus.ru/UserFiles/Image/Knowledges/articles/Slogan_translation.pdf) (08.02.2022).
3. Bernadskaya Yu.S. Tekst v reklame : ucheb. posobie dlya studentov vuzov / Yu.S. Bernadskaya. M. : Yuniti, 2008. – 288 p.
4. Bobrov V. B. Anglo-russkiy slovar' po reklame i marketingu: Okolo 40000 terminov / V. B. Bobrov. M. : Russo, 2004. – 752 p.
5. Dobrosklonskaya T. G. Yazik sredstv massovoy informasii: uchebnoe posobie / T.G. Dobrosklonskaya. M. : KDU, 2008. – 116 p.
6. Krivonosov A.D. Janri PR - teksta: Uchebnoe posobie dlya studentov otdeleniy svyazey s obshestvennost'yu / A.D. Krivonosov. SPb. : Laboratoriya operativnoy pechati fakul'teta jurnalistiki SPbGU, 2001. – 135 p.
7. Mezensev, Ye.A. Reklama v kommunikacionnom prosesse / Ye. A. Mezensev. Omsk : Publishing house of OmGTU, 2007. – 64 p.
8. Mudrov A.N. Osnovi reklami: A. N. Mudrov. M. : Master's, 2008. – 397 p.
9. Kaftandjiev X. Teksti pechatnoy reklami: M. Dimshisa / X. Kaftandjiev. M. : 1995. – 134 p.
10. Kommunikativnie aspekti yazika i kul'turi: sbornik statey X Mejdunarodnoy nauchnoprakticheskoy konferensii studentov i molodix uchyonix. Ch.4. / pod red. S.A. Pesoskoy; Nasional'niy issledovatel'skiy Tomskiy politexnicheskiy universitet. – Tomsk, 2010. – 294 p.